

OPTIMIZATION OF GAMMA RAY SPECTROSCOPY TECHNIQUE FOR MEASUREMENT OF NUCLEAR POLLUTION OF WATER SAMPLES DUE TO URANIUM AND THORIUM SALTS

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Abstract:

Uranium and Thorium are naturally occurring radioactive elements in the earth crust, which emits alpha particles, gamma and beta radiations with long half life of 10^{10} years. Though Uranium and Thorium are used as nuclear fuel in thermal and fast neutron reactor technology for the nuclear power generation, but it is hazardous for living life due to its harmful nuclear radiations. Salts of Uranium and Thorium are water soluble, therefore, they make the nuclear water pollution mostly at coastal areas where Uranium and Thorium storage in the earth crust are found. In view of this, efforts are made to optimize gamma ray spectroscopy technique to determine the concentration level of these radioactive material in water samples. In present work, it has been found that Uranium salt emits gamma radiation of energies 590 KeV, 750 KeV, 980 KeV, 1450 KeV, and Thorium salt emits gamma radiation of energies 340KeV, 570KeV, 910KeV. Concentrations of Uranium and Thorium in water samples are measured using NaI(Tl) gamma ray scintillation detector. Solutions of water samples are prepared with different concentration of Uranium and Thorium salt in the range 5% to 1.25% of Uranium and 1% to 0.125% of Thorium. The minimum detectable levels of concentration of Uranium and Thorium in water samples are found to be 0.058 gm and 0.005gm respectively. Estimated gamma ray activities of this minimum detectable level of the samples are found to be 0.0078Bq and 0.046Bq respectively for Uranium and Thorium. This gives the specific gamma ray activities of 0.1327 Bq/gm and 9.2Bq/gm of Uranium and Thorium in water samples respectively.

Keywords: NaI(Tl) , Gamma Ray Spectrometer, Activity, Uranyl Nitrate, Thorium Nitrate, Nuclear pollution

Introduction:

Salts of Uranium and Thorium are naturally radioactive and decays with their own series resulting into many radioactive nuclides such as Radium-228, Actinium-228, Radium-224, Radon-220, Polonium-216, Lead-212, Bismuth-212, Polonium-212. Many of them are having long half lives. These radioactive products emits alpha, beta and gamma radiations. These radiations are harmful to the living organisms. Uranium and Thorium are available in the form of salts. These salts dissolve into water and make soil and water pollution. Finally, these salts are taken up by the various crops through the water. This results into nuclear pollution in vegetables and food. Its radioactivity possesses increased risks of lung cancer and bone cancer. Uranium and Thorium are also chemically toxic at high concentrations and can cause damage to internal organs, notably the kidneys. Animal studies suggest that Uranium and Thorium may affect reproduction, increase the risk of soft tissue cancer, and drinking massive amounts of it can cause death from metal poisoning. Literature survey shows that the water of the coastal areas of India is naturally contaminated with Uranium and Thorium salts. In view of this, present research work is carried out to estimate trace concentration of Uranium and Thorium salt in water samples.

Experimental Details:

NaI(Tl) gamma ray Spectrometer is calibrated using standard gamma ray sources provided by the B.A.R.C, Mumbai. This Spectrometer is coupled to 8K Multi-Channel Analyzer and computer. Water samples are prepared using Uranium and Thorium salts with different concentration levels in the range of 5% to 1.25% and 1% to 0.125% respectively. For this, standard Thorium nitrate $[\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and Uranyl Nitrate $[\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ are used. Gamma ray activity of each water sample with different concentrations of Uranium and Thorium salt is measured for the gamma ray photo peak of gamma energies 750KeV and 570 KeV respectively. Measured gamma ray activity of each sample is used to estimate the activity of Uranium and Thorium using the efficiency of detector and geometrical factor. From this data, specific activity of the Uranium and Thorium sample are estimated using standard relations.

Table-1 represents gamma ray activities of water samples with different concentration of Uranium and Thorium salts.

Table 1: Measured Gamma Ray Activity of Thorium and Uranium in water samples.

Percentage of Thorium Nitrate in water	Amount of Thorium Nitrate (gm)	Amount of Thorium (gm)	Measured counts for 3600 sec. under photo peak	Estimated Activity (Bq)
100%	1.000	0.400	20786	0.607

1.000%	0.100	0.040	4326	0.126
0.500%	0.050	0.020	2464	0.072
0.250%	0.025	0.010	2213	0.066
0.125%	0.012	0.005	1536	0.046

Percentage of Uranyl Nitrate in water	Amount of Uranyl Nitrate (gm)	Amount Uranium (gm)	of	Measured counts for 3600 sec. under photo peak	Estimated Activity (Bq)
100%	1.000	0.4670		2021	0.1180
5.00%	0.500	0.2335		666	0.0370
2.50%	0.250	0.1167		505	0.0290
1.25%	0.125	0.0583		143	0.0078

Figure-1: Gamma ray spectrum of pure Thorium Nitrate [Th(NO₃)₄.5H₂O] recorded by NaI(Tl) gamma ray detector

Figure-2: Gamma ray spectrum of 1% and 0.125% Thorium Nitrate in water sample

Figure-3: Gamma ray spectrum of pure Uranyl Nitrate [$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] recorded by NaI(Tl) gamma ray detector

Figure-4: Gamma ray spectrum of 5% and 1.25% Uranyl Nitrate in water sample

Results and conclusions:

Gamma ray spectrum of Thorium and Uranium salts given in figure-1 indicates that the Thorium salt [$\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$] emits gamma ray of energies 340 KeV, 570 KeV, 910 KeV and figure-3 indicate that Uranyl Nitrate [$\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] emits gamma ray of energies 590 KeV, 750 KeV, 980 KeV, 1450 KeV.

The intensities of gamma energy 570KeV and 750KeV are found to be more as compared to the other gamma radiations of Thorium and Uranium respectively. These gamma photo peaks are used for analysis in the present work. Gamma ray spectrum of water samples of 1% and 0.125% concentration of Thorium and similarly Gamma ray spectra of water samples of 5% and 1.25% concentration of Uranium are given in fig-2 and fig-4 respectively. This indicate that intensity of gamma radiations has decreased rapidly with decreasing concentration of solution. The results obtained in present work shows that the gamma ray activity of Thorium and Uranium salt in water of minimum level are found to be 0.046 Bq and 0.0078 Bq respectively. These minimum level of detection gives the specific activity of Thorium 9.2 Bq/gm and of Uranium 0.1327 Bq/gm. Results in the current work indicate that the present method can be used to estimate the trace concentration of Uranium and Thorium in water samples and hence can be used to determine the nuclear pollution in water.

Acknowledgement:

Authors are thankful to the P.G.K. Mandal, Pune and the Principal Dr. G.R. Pathade, Haribhai V. Desai College, Pune for laboratory equipments and financial support.

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